

EU Common Fisheries Policy regulation in practice: Lessons from Cypriot fishers

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Introduction

The EU's Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) aims to ensure environmentally sustainable fisheries as the precondition for delivering economic, social, and employment benefits. Its success depends on effective implementation and enforcement by Member States.

With the European Commission's 2026 evaluation of the CFP regulation, and the Republic of Cyprus holding the EU Council Presidency in the first semester of 2026, understanding local implementation, control, and enforcement challenges is vital. Cyprus, an EU member since 2004, is the third-largest Mediterranean island facing pressures common to the region: accelerated climate warming, shifts in native marine species and rapidly spreading invasive ones, a history of overfishing, and a declining traditional commercial sector, despite Cypriot Minister of Agriculture, Rural Development and Environment's commitment to CFP implementation and compliance.

This report draws on surveys of 47 commercial fishers in Cyprus – those most directly affected by the CFP regulation – to assess where measures work, where they fall short, and how gaps in national implementation, control, and enforcement affect the achievement of CFP objectives in practice.

Methodology:

- **Fieldwork:** Three days (December 2025) in six fishing shelters: Larnaca, Latsi, Limassol, Ormidia Fishing Shelter, Paphos, Potamos Liopetri Fishing Shelter.
- **Approach:** Oceana, with support from AP Marine Environmental Consultancy, surveyed fishers in harbours, onboard vessels, and at local meeting points. Surveys were carried out using a three-page questionnaire, with both closed and open questions. Quantitative and qualitative data were validated through triangulation.
- **Sample:** 47 commercial fishers, of which 89.4% fished on small-scale vessels (i.e. <12 m length, 42 fishers), 8.5% on mid-sized vessels (12–18 m length, 4 fishers), and 2.1% on large vessels (>18 m length; 1 fisher). Gears are predominantly passive (gillnets, trammel nets). Of the fishers surveyed, 57.4% have over 30 years of fishing experience, 25.5% have 21-30 years' experience, and 10.6% have 5-10 years' experience.

Findings:

Cypriot fishers described a consistent set of challenges that affect the viability of their activity and, in turn, undermine the achievement of the environmental, social, and economic objectives of the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP).

 Across all ports, **nearly all respondents (96%, n = 45 out of 47) stated that national government action is insufficient.**

Fishers highlighted weak control and enforcement of existing rules and expressed frustration with a lack of effective administrative support to address environmental, social, and economic pressures.

These challenges are examined in more detail in the sections below, which explore environmental pressures on fisheries outcomes, socio-economic and administrative constraints, and fishers' strong support for management measures when they are appropriately designed and enforced.

Environmental pressures affecting CFP outcomes

Declining fish stocks

Fishers consistently reported declining catches and the disappearance of traditional commercial species.

 Around **72% of respondents (n = 34 out of 47) identified stock declines or a lack of fish as a central challenge**, indicating pervasive concerns that current protection and recovery measures are not delivering sufficient results.

“Catches are declining and disappearing because reproduction is not protected.”

Fishers associate these trends with long-standing fishing pressure and insufficient protection of spawning and nursery grounds, within an overall context they perceive as environmentally unsustainable.

Climate-driven ecosystem changes and invasive species

Environmental pressures were widely cited: **68% of respondents** (n = 32/47) mentioned either **climate change or invasive species as directly affecting fishing conditions**, with substantial overlap between the two. Fishers often see these issues as interconnected—warming waters are perceived to facilitate the spread of invasive species, compounding ecological and economic challenges.

Around **85%** (n = 40/47) called for **government action against invasive species**. For example, fishers noted that inconsistent management of invasive species removal programmes within marine protected areas was noted to weaken conservation impact. Apart from Cape Greco MPA, where *Lagocephalus* removal is carried out, most MPAs lack such programmes, allowing invasive species to proliferate.

Additional environmental stressors

Around **43% of respondents** (n = 20 out of 47) identified **pollution as contributing to ecosystem degradation**, including seepage from agricultural land, coastal discharges, aquaculture activity, and tourism-related pollution.

Taken together, declining stocks, climate-driven ecosystem changes, and pollution create strong perceptions among fishers that the environmental objectives of the CFP are not being met in practice.

Support for conservation measures under the CFP

Despite these pressures, fishers expressed strong support for conservation measures when they are fair, effective, and properly enforced:

94% (n = 44 out of 47) support restricting or prohibiting gears in sensitive habitats.

98% (n = 46 out of 47) believe better habitat protection improves stocks over time.

62% (n = 29 out of 47) support fishing capacity limits to manage overall effort. Among these supporters, about **76%** (n = 22 of 29) believe, however, such ceilings can restrict safety and comfort.

57% (n = 27 out of 47) consider reducing unwanted catches important.

“ There must be closures for specific months. For example, March, April, and May, which are the spawning months... And they must say clearly: “we will compensate you so that you do not go out fishing,” to allow fish to reproduce...”

Some fishers noted positive national actions taken over the years, including restrictions on trawlers to protect *Posidonia* meadows and artificial reef deployment that has locally increased fish abundance.

Socio-economic impacts and viability

An ageing workforce and limited renewal

Surveyed respondents reflect the ageing nature of the Cypriot fishing sector:

64% of respondents (n = 30 out of 47) were aged 55 or older, while

only 2% (n = 1 out of 47) were aged 25-34.

This imbalance signals weak generational renewal despite high accumulated experience (57% with more than 30 years at sea).

“ When the time comes for them to leave... there will be no continuity.”

Concerns about the future and generational renewal are widespread. Around 70% of respondents (n = 33 out of 47) expressed challenges to continuity of the profession and lack of young entrants.

Cumulative cost pressures

Fishers face sustained cost burdens:

- 75% (n = 35 out of 47) reported that compensation for gear damage is not always available.
- 70% (n = 33 out of 47) reported long delays in receiving compensation payments.
- 51% (n = 24 out of 47) reported high operational costs (fuel, gear, VAT, bait).
- 47% (n = 22 out of 47) reported frequent gear damage from protected megafauna (dolphins, turtles, seals).

“ The nets we need to buy are very expensive. And it’s not just the cost of buying them. You also have to sew them. For me to sit down and sew one net, I need three or four full days of work...I lose my daily income from the sea during those days until the nets are ready.”

Administrative burdens and constrained income opportunities

Fishers described administrative arrangements that reduce financial resilience, including complex port-sale invoicing rules.

Several respondents pointed to perverse incentives that discourage accurate catch reporting, with pressure to over-declare catches in order to maintain licences or access EU funds.

Lack of access to quota species further limits income diversification for many coastal fishers.

“ We, as coastal fishermen, are not allowed to catch albacore tuna, bluefin tuna, or yellowfin tuna, even though some of these species exist in the Mediterranean. I believe this is wrong. It could give me an opportunity to earn a day’s income... These are small opportunities... and could give me a small financial breathing space...”

Positive social and economic measures recognised by fishers

“ In recent years, they have started subsidising us for catching silver-cheeked toadfish. This is very, very helpful for fishermen, but that’s the only support we get. We catch them, there are groups that collect them, we give them the fish, and they pay us 3 euros per kilo.”

Fishers acknowledged national measures that have provided some socio-economic relief, including targeted compensation for gear damage caused by protected species and specific payments for removing certain invasive species.

Recommendations

1) Prioritise effective national implementation of existing CFP rules and partnership with fishers

What fishers say: Around **96% of respondents** stated that national government support is insufficient to address the challenges facing fisheries. Approximately **70%** reported uncertainty linked to frequent EU rule changes, while only **28%** consider CFP reform itself a priority and fishers emphasise that Mediterranean and Cypriot

conditions are not well served by a one-size-fit all approach. Beyond rules, fishers consistently ask to be treated as partners.

“Laws that exist only on paper achieve nothing.”

Recommended actions for the Cypriot ministry and its services:

- Provide clear guidance and timely implementation support.
- Prioritise the use of CFP regionalisation mechanisms and national implementation flexibilities to adapt measures to the realities of Mediterranean and Cypriot fisheries.
- Establish regular dialogues between authorities and fishers at the national level.

“They need to come closer to the fishermen and see them as partners.”

2) Restore fish stocks and protect critical habitats

What fishers say: Approximately **72% of respondents** identified declining fish stocks or lack of fish as a central challenge. Around **94%** support restricting or prohibiting gears in sensitive habitats, and **98%** believe improved habitat protection leads to stock recovery over time, provided measures are applied consistently across all fishing activities and supported by compensation during closures.

Recommended actions for the Cypriot ministry and its services:

- Implement seasonal closures based on verified data, applied across all fishing activities, including recreational fishing.
- Link closures to reliable and timely compensation.

3) Make the landing obligation economically workable

What fishers say: Approximately **87% of respondents** identified lack of market value as the primary driver of unwanted catches, followed by undersized fish (**68%**), and poisonous species (**17%**). Fishers stressed that without economic outlets or compensation, compliance with the landing obligation generates direct financial losses.

Recommended actions for the Cypriot ministry and its services:

- Invest in infrastructure for handling unwanted catches (recommended by **66% of respondents**).
- Introduce economic incentives for landing low-value species, such as promoting low-value species to consumers (recommended by **32% of respondents**).
- Provide targeted financial aid for handling unwanted catches (recommended by **9% of respondents**).
- Increase stock-recovery measures to rebuild stocks and reduce undersized catches (recommended by **98% of respondents**).

4) Prevent, reduce and adapt to invasive species

What fishers say: Around **85%** (n = 40/47) called for government action against invasive species.

Recommended actions for the Cypriot ministry and its services:

- Improve research and mapping of invasive species.
- Implement coherent removal programmes, including in MPAs.
- Ensure reliable and timely compensation for gear damage and removal programmes (recommended by **75% of respondents**).
- Develop markets and value chains for invasive species.

5) Ensure fair and consistent enforcement across all fishing activities

What fishers say: Fishers across multiple ports reported sustained pressure from recreational fishing (**83%**), with a clear call for better control and enforcement (**77%**), including improvements to licensing systems and the use of Vessel Monitoring Systems (VMS). Fishers highlighted illegal fishing activity, particularly within coastal and protected areas, as a consequence of weak oversight. Respondents stressed that unequal application of rules between commercial and recreational fishing undermines compliance, and conservation outcomes.

Recommended actions for the Cypriot ministry and its services:

- Strengthen monitoring, control, and surveillance across all fishing activities, including recreational fishing, in proportion to fishing pressure.
- Improve and enforce licensing systems, compliance checks, and sanctions where rules are breached.
- Apply existing EU requirements for electronic monitoring of commercial and recreational vessels.
- Intensify action against illegal fishing, particularly in coastal waters and marine protected areas, to ensure that conservation rules apply equally to all users.

6) Secure socio-economic viability and reduce administrative burdens

What fishers say: Around **70% of respondents** (n = 33 out of 47) expressed challenges to continuity of the profession and lack of young entrants. Approximately **87%** support access to quota-managed species to improve income resilience, **83%** support rewarding low-impact fishing, and **53%** support introducing safeguards against quota concentration. During interviews across ports, fishers highlighted that existing administrative arrangements discourage accurate reporting rather than supporting compliance.

Recommended actions for the Cypriot ministry and its services:

- Explore and facilitate access to quota-managed species for coastal fishers to improve income, introduce rewards for the use of low-impact fishing practices and gear, and establish safeguards against quota concentration.
- Reduce incentives for inaccurate catch declarations.
- Simplify administrative procedures and provide administrative support services.
- Support preferential (and in some cases exclusive) coastal access for commercial fishers (supported by **70% of respondents**).

7) Ensure EU-level support in addressing climate-driven changes

What fishers are asking for: Fishers consistently describe climate change as a cross-border pressure that cannot be addressed at the national level alone.

Recommended actions for the European Commission:

- Strengthen EU support for scientific data collection, stock assessment, and monitoring of climate-driven changes in species distribution and productivity.
- Promote coordinated Mediterranean approaches to climate impacts, recognising shared ecosystems and cross-border stocks.

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